

Global Research Protocol

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Post-pandemic resilient communities: is the informal economy a reservoir for the next generation of digitalized and green businesses in the Global South?

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Abstract

This document develops a common research protocol for the PRESILIENT project to sustain the mix of qualitative and quantitative approaches, featuring a list of major methods that can be used for data collection and analysis, and fostering coherence of the work carried out within the project in different 15 settings in the Global South. The document is specifically devoted to outlining the protocols in research working packages (WP1 Horizon Scanning; WP2 Delphi Survey; WP3 Interpretation and Production), and also in guiding research training (WP4) and dissemination, exploitation, and follow-up deliverables (WP5). This protocol is also linked with the Data Management Plan, although it is a separate deliverable (Task 6.3), and with the (WP7) that sets out 'ethics requirements' for the whole project. The protocol provides essential guidelines on addressing the research questions choosing and integrating different research methods using the appropriate methodologies to generate new theoretical insights through the analysis of the empirical material collected in different settings.

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1. Introduction

The purpose of this deliverable (Task1.1) is to develop a common research protocol for the PRESILIENT project to sustain the mix of qualitative and quantitative approaches, featuring a list of major methods that can be used for data collection and analysis, and fostering coherence of the work carried out within the project in different 15 settings in the Global South. This document is specifically devoted to outlining the protocols in research working packages (WP1 Horizon Scanning; WP2 Delphi Survey; WP3 Interpretation and Production), but also in guiding research training (WP4) and dissemination, exploitation, and follow-up deliverables (WP5). This protocol is also linked with the Data Management Plan, although it is a separate deliverable (Task 6.3), and with the (WP7) that sets out ‘ethics requirements’ for the whole project. Presented and validated at the first project network event, this protocol provides essential guidelines on:

- 1) How to develop relevant research questions starting from existent theory.
- 2) How to choose and integrate different research methods and approaches.
- 3) How to use empirical material collected to generate new theoretical insights by addressing the research questions with the appropriate methods and data.

The PRESILIENT project, “Post-pandemic resilient communities: is the informal economy a reservoir for the next generation of digitalized and green businesses in the Global South?”, is committed to being a cutting-edge response to the current precariousness of employment and re-emerging informality in the Global South. It does so by engaging a broad and diverse network of 14 partners (of which 7 are non-academic), and 15 associated partners located in Africa, Asia-Pacific, and Latin America (one per target country), which will collect and process data. It will lead to a deeper understanding of the causes and dynamics of informality, produce valuable policy recommendations. Moreover, it is committed to delivering a world-class cross-regional training on

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informality in the Global South to: measure it, address it, and find viable and sustainable alternatives.

The project has the following objectives:

- O.1.** Train the next generation of experts on informality in the Global South;
- O.2.** Carry out research spanning 15 different countries and produce novel data and significant theoretical advancements in the field;
- O.3.** Produce strategic intelligence that can be used to provide practical policy recommendations;
- O.4.** Enable multi-directional knowledge transfer through network events, the pairing of academic and non-academic partners (who will jointly supervise each fellow), secondment and task-based teamwork.

PRESILIENT research spans over 15 countries (Vietnam, Colombia, Kyrgyzstan, Thailand, Ecuador, Mexico, New Guinea, Brazil, Senegal, Kenya, Morocco, Chile, Zambia, Indonesia and Bolivia) with diverse social, economic, cultural and environmental characteristics. Aware of this challenge, our methodology has been designed to secure a high degree of consistency in data collection to make results comparable, while also remaining open to possible specificities in each case. This includes the possibility that the loci of informality may differ significantly from one country to another. Achieving this balance between mid-range generalizing comparisons and individualizing specificities will be possible by relying on three main methodological steps: Horizon Scanning, Delphi survey and Case Studies (using personal network data, see below). This protocol provides the widest possible overview of the variety of methods at the disposal of Early Stage Researchers (ESRs), and how they can be used and combined while leaving room for individual initiative and novel approaches that can help ESRs to better address their research questions.

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2. Phases of research and project methodology

PRESILIENT's methodological approach has been divided into five phases. Each phase of the project will be composed of a 1) training and a 2) research component to ensure that ESRs acquire the necessary competencies to contribute to the different stages of research.

Figure 1. Project phases.

The first phase is devoted to developing relevant research questions starting from existing theory. Fellows will develop the tools to engage with theory, complete research design, conduct institutional analysis and plan data collection. Each ESR will develop their individual research questions that should be aligned with the main general research questions of PRESILIENT:

1. What are the sectors that have been mostly affected by the pandemic in the target countries?
2. What are the most promising sectors that could lead to economic recovery in each of the target countries?
3. What are the most appropriate policy responses to the current situation?

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The research questions must be guided by the recent debates on informality, in special by three interpretative frameworks: (1) Empirical analysis highly embedded in social, policy and cultural contexts, (2) Theorization that conceives informality beyond a merely economic phenomenon, and (3) Use of research findings to inform policies in this field.

In the second and third phases of research, while macro-data for Horizon Scanning can follow a global approach, the construction of the Delphi Survey must take into account local specificities that also will inform the data collection tools used for Case Studies. This degree of flexibility, embedded in a common approach, provides the space to treat ESRs as individuals with different, and unique career paths, preferences and career aspirations giving them the option of engaging with suitable and relevant alternative methodologies. Each ESR will work together with their supervisor, mentors and WP leaders to align their research questions to the overarching focus of the research, allowing exchanges within and between WPs leading to cross-pollination between disciplines.

The research team will encourage the use of mixed methods (using a combination of both qualitative and quantitative data collection methods) where relevant to research questions. Empirical analysis (data collection and processing) will primarily be the responsibility of each ESR, who will acquire the necessary skills through network training events and through individually tailored advice (from supervisors and mentors) to put them into practice through a learn-by-doing exercise in data collection and analysis. In Phases 4 and 5, the final theorization, generalization and dissemination efforts will be a collective exercise through which individually generated data will be interpreted and merged into overall conclusions thanks to coordination between WP leaders and members of the research team.

This overall research plan overlaps with individual PhD research plans looking for mutual synergies. Following the guidelines and protocols of this document (among other requirements), each ESR will submit a **Data Collection Plan (DCP)** to their supervisors,

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which will then be presented to the network and discussed with WP leaders and the Supervisory Board (SB) to ensure its quality, feasibility and the coherence of the aggregate of plans to the projects' objectives.

3. Research Methods

3.1. Horizon Scanning

Horizon Scanning (HS) is a tool for “a systematic examination of information to identify potential threats, risks, emerging issues, and opportunities” (House of Commons, 2014). The HS methodology has been often used for collectively researching emerging phenomena (most probable not present on current agendas) through the identification of (often weak and early) signals and organizing information in clusters (Konnola et al., 2012; Tsakalidis et al., 2021) (Konnola et al., 2012; Tsakalidis et al., 2021). The project PRESILIENT aims to apply this method to 15 countries looking for economic and social trends in 15 Countries. To achieve this purpose, the 15 ESRs will provide the necessary information to build a common dataset able to accomplish this purpose following the same procedures.

Horizon Scanning on Economic and Social Trends in 15 Countries

The goal of this exercise is to “understand what’s going on in each country with regard to the economic trends. Our aim is not to chase the informal economy directly but to describe the trends starting from very basic questions: what went down and what went up.

- 1) What are the most vulnerable sectors of the economy? What sectors faced hardship as a result of the pandemic? This means to check pre-2019 levels and then the following years. Those that went down are likely to be the most vulnerable to asymmetric shocks.

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2) What are the most promising sectors of the economy? During the pandemic, some sectors saw a boom at least in some countries (i.e. online services, food delivery, streaming services, digital contents). Not all of them remained at the same level once the pandemic was over.

All ESRs will keep in mind that the growth of a sector may not be absolute and a sector, an industry, a company, may grow significantly without the situation of workers improving (or even degenerating). Therefore, when addressing points 1 and 2, ESRs may want to complement it with socio-economic indicators and, after looking at the surface, rephrase the questions

1.0) What sectors saw a higher level of volatility, vulnerability and precariousness during the pandemic? Who took the risk for new (or existing) business initiatives, in what sectors, companies, industries workers had to bare most of the costs of the pandemic?

2.0) In what sectors (if any) workers were able to gain some advantages, get some security, organize between them to create business and activities that helped them out of poverty, precariousness and if possible keep sustaining their businesses?

Questions 1 and 1.0, as well as 2 and 2.0, might not overlap, in some cases workers lost security while their bosses made money and vice versa.

Data collection, Exportation and Analysis

An important task (1.2) is to conceptualize, discuss and share guidelines for HS exercise with indications of the main approaches and sources that could be used. It will entail coordinating with regional partners to ensure criteria and approaches take into account local nuances (e.g. including scanning processes in more than one language). The task will be approached as a collective exercise, with individual research projects acting as building blocks for integration into the WP's wide perspectives. The HS will be supervised and supported by all ESRs, followed by discussions on findings and cross-regional comparisons. The teams will engage in a systematic gathering of data to identify existing

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and early signs of potentially important developments and possible emerging trends for the identified focal points of interest. The Horizon Scanning will be used to search local, national, regional, and statistical sources on informality, make state-of-the-art academic and grey kinds of literature, and identify experts and find future current and future trends.

The protocol of the Horizon Scanning has three phases:

Phase 1. Keywords.

To be able to generate a visual representation of the exercise, we will need to move through keywords. We will take advantage of having many different people from various background to share these keywords. In a shared document each ESR will add their keywords (the ones used for searching). This will inspire others to use keywords that they find useful and, in the end, allow us to identify 10-15 keywords that will become common and will be used for all searches to have a consistent database.

Phase 2. Searching.

Each ESR will identify sources but also tendencies based on desk research, and draw from:

- a) population statistics (gender, age groups, urban-rural divide);
- b) economic and welfare indicators (growth, development indices, main sectors of the economy, imports and exports);
- c) policy indicators (country strategy, diplomatic relations, relations with international organizations, strategic plan of the country);
- d) values, needs, expectations of the population (as measured by the World Value Survey);
- e) literature review (articles, reports, policy papers); and
- f) interviews with decision-makers, experts, and analysts contacted thanks to PRESILIENT partners' networks.

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g) social media/blogs/forums

Special attention will be paid to the following sources:

- Official statistics offices;
- International Organisations (ILO, World Bank, Asia/Africa/Latin America Development Bank);
- development organisations (USAID, Europe-aid, Trocaire, Irish aid);
- academic studies (where available);
- newspaper articles (if they cite a study, you can go all the way up to their source);
- reportages, documentaries, business reports by private organisations (i.e. control risks or other organisations providing intelligence about whether to invest in that given country);
- trade union reports and documents (where available)

All ESRs will search and collect in format APA 6a edition:

1. A systematic review of academic references following the keywords.
2. A systematic review of media posts, articles, interviews or comments.
3. Grey literature, including databases, reports, or statistical sources.

The reference manager (Zotero) provides templates for three required sources of information. The title, abstract and keywords should be provided in English. Also, each ESR will write a 2-3 page report answering the following questions:

1) What were the sectors of the economy that faced the most issues, declined or even collapsed as a result of the COVID crisis? This shall be assessed as a marginal decrease from the pre-covid situation.

1.1) Why were these sectors the most vulnerable, volatile? What were the causes that signed their decline? Do they have anything in common? Was the decline a result of geo-economic, environmental, cultural change? or other? (i.e. highly

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dependent on imports and closed borders did not allow, obsolete technology, no longer needed).

2) What were the sectors that boomed or saw an increase as a result of the COVID crisis? This shall be assessed as a marginal (substantial) increase from the pre-covid situation.

2.1) What allowed these sectors to flourish? (i.e. technological innovation? culture change - e.g. masks and sanitary material -, psychological reactions - i.e. more cooking at home-).

3) How sustainable/unsustainable/maintained is the growth/decline in the sectors at points 1 and 2? Can they be expected to continue this way?

4) What innovations have been consolidated in the country and will, most likely, remain or improve in the next years (opinion but based on data/evidence gathered through the exercise)?

Phase 3. Analysis

Once the information is collected by each ESR and the data is delivered, the PRESILIENT team will compile and curate a dataset. With aid of R packages, the analysis will represent the temporal evolution of emergent topics at the global level and for each country, particularly for 2020-2023, information that will be shared within the Consortium. Theme detection using the packages available for this purpose in R (among others `quanteda`, `tm`, `topic models`, `tidytext`, `text2vec`, `word2vec`, `stm`, `textmineR`). With these packages it is possible to implement quantitative analysis such as Topic Analysis with LDA, Latent semantic analysis (LSA), n-gram and correlations, feeling analysis, or word embedding with GloVe (Stanford) or word2vec (Google). For grey literature, LDA and LSA have been often used, as David Blei has shown by analyzing 100 topics of diverse disciplines from 17,000 articles in the Science journal (Blei, 2012). Finally, this method would also be used for identifying experts, which will be very convenient for the Delphi method in the next phase of research, identifying novel/frequent topics with experts and their networks.

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Once the ESRs review the outputs provided by the automatic theme detection analysis, a compiled report summarising the main findings will be shared with SB and WP2 leader to inform the Delphi Survey.

3.2. Delphi survey

A Delphi survey, a methodological tool often used “to generate insights on controversial topics with limited information” (Beiderbeck et al., 2021), will be used to identify emerging trends and challenges in each country and what possible sectors, approaches, and incentives can move informal actors into more viable, green and sustainable alternatives. Based on the results of the previous phase and the tendencies identified by the preliminary Horizon Scanning exercise, a questionnaire for the Delphi survey will be conceptualized at the beginning of the phase and shared with regional partners (WP2, UB lead).

The questionnaire will have a common part A but also a part B taking into account the specificities of the country surveyed that will emerge from the results of the HS exercise as well as consultation with regional partners. This learning-by-doing approach will foster autonomy by requiring ESRs to independently engage in fieldwork, overcoming challenges in data collection (identifying and approaching informants, sampling, approaching institutions). Local partners will also be crucial in the identification of experts (depending on country size) for the Delphi survey. Participation in the Delphi will also help ESRs to identify key informants, issues and tendencies for the constructions of the Case Studies for which individual methodological choices will be the responsibility of ESRs, with guidance from their supervising team.

Based in the region and well embedded in their expert communities and familiar with the local context, regional partners will be vital in adapting data collection approaches and the survey instrument itself to local specificities and ensuring that the proper questions are asked most effectively. Local partners will also be crucial in the identification of experts (depending on country size) for three rounds of the Delphi

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survey. We expect a moderate attrition through waves foreseen about 90 experts in wave one and 60 in wave three. The main local contact will act as the questionnaire facilitator for each target country. Being involved in the Delphi survey will be a crucial element for the construction of professional networks by ESRs, their training and in furtherance of their research. Not only will each ESR establish contact with some of the most important experts in their target countries, some of whom may become future collaborators, employers, mentors or peers.

Figure 2. Methodology of the Delphi survey.

We will consider a common technical approach by using the same software for conducting the analysis (e.g. Calibrium or other dedicated tools, Aengenheyster et al.,

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2017), respectively some common paths for the analytical strategies to ensures potential comparisons (e.g. sentiment analyses, scenario analyses).

3.3. Case studies

The Case Studies will be used to test these preliminary findings and check the reaction of the target groups (people, business actors, marginalized groups) of the possible measures identified through the Delphi survey. The ultimate goal of this exercise (WP3, led by UAB) is to produce in-depth case studies (at least two for each ESR) that shall complement the data collected through previous approaches. Both results of the survey and the individually produced case studies will be presented and validated at a network event.

Each ESR will produce (at least) two in-depth case studies using a combination of methods. A case study is an in-depth investigation of a particular group of people, event, organization or person. The main characteristics of a case study is that have demarcated boundaries, evolves in time and in a specific place, is intensive (rich, complete) and has a deep relation with the social context (Denzin & Lincoln, 2017). ESRs will refer to this research protocol and select a combination of the following methods, although they have also autonomy to use other methods:

- 1) **In-depth interviews** with key actors (e.g. policy planners, urban planners, decision-makers, entrepreneurs, business managers, religious and community leaders, workers of international organizations, and civil servants, as appropriate) will be carried out by ESRs. A detailed informed consent (see Annex 1 in this document) must be signed by the researcher/interviewer and the interviewee before starting the interview. Ideally, between 10 and 20 interviews of an hour long (audio-recorded) must be performed. A semi-structured guide will be prepared before the interview and one pilot test should be done to refine the topics, questions, and structure. The audio recordings will be transcribed and anonymized for analysis using a computer computer-assisted qualitative data analysis software (CAQDAS) such as NVIVO or Atlas.ti. At the end of the project, the anonymized transcripts will be uploaded to a secure server and the audio recordings deleted from all the hardware devices. In some situations in which the recording may influence the answers, informal interviews with scripts made from

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notes taken during the interview -which requires training-, might be a more suitable method (Rutakumwa et al., 2020) although it must be justified.

- 2) **Focus groups** with target populations (e.g. precarious workers, households, young people, micro-entrepreneurs, businesspeople, company managers, NGO representatives, development workers, and sellers) will be carried out by ESRs. The focus groups will have between 6 and 10 participants who do not know each other. A detailed informed consent (see Annex 1 in this document) must be signed by the interviewer and each participant before starting the focus group. A semi-structured guide will be prepared before the focus group and tested before if possible. ESRs will moderate the discussion. The audio recordings will be transcribed and anonymized for analysis using a CAQDAS. At the end of the project, the anonymized transcripts will be uploaded to a secure server and the audio recordings deleted from all the hardware devices.
- 3) **Participant observation.** ESRs will be based in their target countries and will have sufficient opportunity to choose observation and interaction at sites such as shops, schools, and community or faith-based organizations, among others. Each ESR will collect data in (1) their ethnographic diaries that will be for their private use; (2) observation sheets (a template will be developed) with observations of specific events, contexts, and practices that will be anonymized and uploaded to the repository for comparative analysis. Other ethnographic materials such as photos, videos, or drawings might be included in the observations.
- 4) **Personal network analysis** with key actors and target populations. The selection may prioritize those actors who have been interviewed before (in interviews or have participated in focus groups) or key informants who have been met during participant observation. Previous interactions create some rapport (trust) that will facilitate the questions on the personal network, and combining techniques with the same actor can give extra information for a case study. The aim is that each ESR will collect the personal networks of 10 research participants. Each participant will be asked to provide 25 alteri -people this person knows, who will be nodes in his/her personal network-, and some information about them. The software Network Canvas will help to collect the networks using a common

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interview guide that will be discussed and developed. The network data will be anonymized and uploaded to the repository for comparative analysis.

Figure 3. Methodology overview.

3.4. Analyses tools

The data collected in the previous phase will be anonymized, coded (using a CAQDAS for qualitative and “R” for quantitative data), encrypted, and uploaded to an open-access online repository for use and sharing (in line with EU data protection guidelines). Interpretation of the data will happen at two levels. First, ESRs will work with their supervisors and mentors to assess the implications of their collected material and draw appropriate conclusions. Results and conclusions will then be shared with WP leaders who will then construct a narrative that brings the results from across regions together and will support ESRs in the production of a policy brief and recommendations while also coordinating the production of scientific articles.

The use of common software by all participants will be stimulated to smooth the research process. During the first two events, emphasis will be placed on deciding and having access and knowledge of use in the common software, using free and open-

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source software when possible. Along with a CAQDAS, R, and Network Canvas, the free and open-source software Zotero will be used for reference management. The reviewed references related to the project will be available at the PRESILIENT GROUP at ZOTERO. Only members can view your group online and must be invited to join. All participants will have access to the folder with references and texts in PDF if available. It is important to keep the shared folder updated to facilitate citations and quotations.

<https://www.zotero.org/groups/>

4. Crosscutting research dimensions

4.1. Integration of methods

Research and training on informal economies is, by its nature, multidisciplinary, involving specialists from economics, politics, sociology, anthropology, human geography, and management. PRESILIENT brings together networks of academics, industry experts, and consultants to bridge across disciplines, regions, and sectors in a way that is, in many respects, unique. As a result, the primary PhD training of each ESR will be embedded in different disciplines depending on the university of enrolment but will then be complemented by:

- a) network events in which researchers from other disciplines will participate (and deliver modules);
- b) recruitment at non-academic organizations with different research and training approaches;
- c) secondment in the target region in an institution from another disciplinary background;

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d) completion of network tasks in teams featuring diverse disciplinary approaches.

The approach outlined in PRESILIENT has been developed as a result of several meetings between network researchers and combines qualitative and quantitative elements drawn from future studies, development studies, economics, management as well as qualitative approaches used in sociology, anthropology and geography; each of which has been represented in the SB and research team. Research design and development will follow a similar approach with all partners working together, each bringing contributions from their disciplines. Validation and quality control will be the responsibility of the SB, which is diverse and inclusive both in its nature and disciplinary approach to further foster the interdisciplinarity of the research. The same can be said for follow-up that will be built on inter-disciplinary discussions. The dissemination strategy will follow a similar approach, will take into account the multi-disciplinarity of the research and engage with a variety of outlets (both regional and/or in-area studies) to tailor knowledge transfer for different audiences.

4.2. Gender dimension

PRESILIENT is committed to paying close attention to gender dimensions at all stages of the project. In addition to administrative measures (gender balance in the SB and employment conditions), the research plan integrates gender concerns and gender sensitivity in all the phases of the methodology. ESRs will receive gender training at the beginning of the project to take into account the gender dimension in the deployment of their methodology. The Horizon Scanning phase will take into account specific reports on female conditions in each of the target countries; the selection of experts for the Delphi survey will be done following gender balance principles. The data collection methods will include several gender-specific questions. Interpretation of results will take into account the cultural and socio-economic specificities of each reality (supporting analysis, for example, of why there are fewer men/women in a given sector compared to other target countries). Finally, results and policy measures will take into account gender and propose mitigations to issues identified and will be conveyed to

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organizations that have a specific focus on gender (WIEGO, UNWomen, ILO, FAO, WB) and will be enhanced by the presence of partners and team members specifically dealing with Women in the Informal Economy (WIEGO, UNWomen, EPRC).

Finally, to ensure that the Gender Dimensions are included along the whole process of research, it is compulsory for each ESR to follow the Toolkit gender in EU-funded research¹ as it is described in Figure 4.

Figure 4. Gender toolbox.

4.3. Open science practices

In line with the recently approved DCU research management policy, PRESILIENT is fully committed to open science practices. At event 2, ESRs will participate in a special open-

¹ <https://op.europa.eu/en/publication-detail/-/publication/c17a4eba-49ab-40f1-bb7b-bb6faaf8dec8>

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access module updating them on the status of open-access debates and EC requirements for research projects. They will be briefed on the need for an open-access culture to:

- a) build new findings on previous research results that shall be shared to improve the quality of results;
- b) encourage collaboration and avoid duplication;
- c) speed-up innovation; and
- d) involve citizens and society through enhanced transparency of scientific practices and results.

At the open access training ESRs will also be informed about the EC recommended path to open access publication that involves:

- 1) Make use of the ORE platform <https://open-research-europe.ec.europa.eu/> for feedback and open access, deposit a post-review or pre-print of the publication (or a dataset generated by the project) in suitable repositories. OpenAIRE will be our entry point to choose the repository. Bibliographic metadata shall include information about the donor (EU), the name of the action and the grant number.
- 2) Provide open access to the publication through self-archiving (after the embargo period, where relevant). DCU's open access support desk will instruct partners to use, where possible, the **model amendment to the publishing agreement** created by the EC to speed up accessibility to the paper. ESR and partners will also be encouraged to identify high-level publishers that have a special agreement with PRESILIENT partner libraries (and thus gold open access can be purchased with a significant discount). The dissemination protocol will take into account both gold and diamond open access and include a list of highly-reputed journals fully open access (diamond open access) with publication scope fitting the scope of our project.

4.4. Ethics

Research in informal economy calls for the high standard on ethics research, often asking indirect questions and protecting participant's identities. This is the reason why during

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the project research will combine written and oral informed consent procedures, depending on the specific situation (Düvell et al. 2010).

From a formal clearance point of view, the coordinator institution must gain approval by its Research Ethics Committee (REC) about the whole project and its specific WPs. Afterwards, each ESR, in collaboration with his/her supervisors, must gain approval from its own REC before starting fieldwork.

Annex I provides a template of the Informed Consent form. In case of oral consent, ESRs should follow the instructions of Annex II. Informed Consent should be gained from all participants and keep in a secure place during 5 years. The information collected will be confidential and store in a secure server for academic purposes only the time necessary to achieve the research project goals.

Apart from the Consent forms, and the ethics approvals, the project will develop a incidental findings policy, a risk mitigation strategy, and a plan to avoid stigmatisation of vulnerable populations:

- *Incidental findings policy.* During the fieldwork unexpected situations may appear and the ESRs will contact with their local partners and their supervisors to address them adequately. ESRs will receive specific training on this matter.
- *Risk mitigation strategy.* The risk mitigation strategy will outline a number of scenarios, precautions and strategies for ensuring the safety of research participants and researchers.
- *Plan to avoid stigmatisation of vulnerable populations.* The research will not specifically seek out individuals in a vulnerable population in their respective countries or from a minority background but the project will develop a policy to adequately protect these populations during the research phases, including dissemination.

All data collected by the project from third parties will be managed under the guidelines of the Data Management Plan.

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4.5. Data management plan

A complete Data Management Plan will be developed for deliverable 6.4. (WP4, led by DCU) and uploaded in <https://argos.openaire.eu/home>. PRESILIENT will generate three kinds of data: processing, elaboration and reinterpretation of existing data (Horizon Scanning exercise), novel data collected through expert surveys (Delphi), and further qualitative data collected through focus groups, expert interviews, etc. that will be managed in line with FAIR principles. By the end of each data collection exercise, the data collected will be validated by the SB and encoded in each university repository for the primary use of the ESR. Data will be made accessible to all consortium members for cross-use in ESR research projects and subsequent publications. Data will likewise be made accessible to senior members of the team and SB for further validation and quality check, where necessary. Once ESRs have been able to use data collected for their doctoral projects and publications (i.e by the end of the project), it will be made findable and accessible in Zenodo <https://zenodo.org/> accompanied by a README file outlining the used methodology and indicators. Where relevant, further repositories supporting DOI will be identified through OPENAire. Given the nature of the research and the methodological approach adopted, we foresee being able to encode the three datasets into a repository (after the anonymization of respondents) and keep them openly accessible. The databases will be registered under Creative Commons licenses to be made reusable with minimal possible limitations. The type of license (BY/NC/SA/ND) will ultimately be defined by the SB once the usability and operability of the data become clear. The thesaurus for economics classification will be the starting reference to identify and choose keywords to make the data findable and interoperable. Should the research produce data that the SB considers sensitive, the PC will discuss with the PO possible restricted access to some of the data produced, keeping in mind the general approach and commitment to the accessibility of data arising from the GA.

4.6. Training in research methods

In the first and second phases of the project, the ESRs will receive specific training in research methods. The plan is to provide specific training on the methods used within

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the project but also more general methods such as Ethnographic Fieldwork, Social Network Analysis with Network Canvas, or Media Analysis, among others. Moreover, a specialized training session will be developed for network event 3 that will be devoted to data collection approaches.

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Annex I – Template for the Informed Consent Form

Informed Consent Form Interview – Focus Group (over-18s)

Post-pandemic resilient communities: is the informal economy a reservoir for the next generation of digitalized and green businesses in the Global South? (PRESILIENT)

Please read this consent form carefully before deciding whether to take part in this study.

Purpose of the research

PRESILIENT is a large network comprising 14 partners (of which 7 non- academic) and 15 associated partners located in Africa, Asia-Pacific and Latin America committed to delivering cross-regional training on informality in the Global South to: measure it, address it, find viable and sustainable alternatives (<https://www.presilient-dn.eu/>).

What participation in the study involves

First of all, we will ask you (...). Then ... Finally,... (...)

Duration

The (research method) takes around (X) minutes.

Risks and benefits

Your participation involves no risks of any kind.

Compensation

In this case, no compensation is envisaged for taking part.

Confidentiality

If you decide to take part, your identity will remain confidential and only members of the research team will have access to the project data. Pseudonyms will always be used if case studies need to be presented.

This informed consent form will be kept in a safe place by the principal investigators and will be destroyed five years after the end of the project. When the project is over and all data have been analysed, the whole database will be anonymised and made available to other interested researchers.

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Voluntary participation

Participation in this study is completely voluntary. There is no penalty for opting not to take part.

Right to withdraw from the study

You can withdraw from the study at any time without giving explanations and with no negative consequences: just by letting us know through any communication channel. As well as this, you can exercise your rights under the European General Data Protection Regulation by making a request to _____ (*indicate the name and surname of the person responsible for the treatment and his/her e-mail address*), enclosing a photocopy of your ID document. Request forms for this purpose are available on the website of the (DPO).

You may also file a claim before the Data Protection Authority (National one). In all cases you will receive a written response within the legal time limit, stating what action has been taken.

Subsequent publication/re-use/other processing of the basic data and conservation period

Research data will be made available in anonymised form to other researchers after 5 years from the end of the project. Personal identifiers will be _____ (*destroyed/securely kept confidential until DATE/securely kept confidential until the objectives of the research project are achieved*).

Recordings and use of contributions made

I agree to the interview being recorded (audio/video) for research purposes.

I consent to my contributions being quoted literally with no mention of my name and to audio or video recordings of my statements being played back with no mention of my name.

I consent to the use of my contributions in audio or video recordings for purposes of scientific dissemination, provided steps are taken to safeguard my privacy.

Contact person

If you have any queries, you can contact the following: (PI of the research project, email address, phone number, postal address).

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Consent

- I have read the information about the research project and I have had the opportunity to ask questions, which have been answered to my satisfaction.
- I understand that the anonymised information (with no personal identifiers) on this project will be placed at the disposal of other researchers some time after the project has ended.
- I agree to take part and I have received a copy of this consent form.

Full name of the participant _____

Signature _____ Date:

Researcher:

Signature _____ Date:

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Annex II – Oral Script

Full oral information giving and consent seeking process

Record this consent process using a digital recorder (if participant has consented to this or by using the Record of Consent Form)

Post-pandemic resilient communities: is the informal economy a reservoir for the next generation of digitalized and green businesses in the Global South? (PRESILIENT)

Project description

Hello, my name is [insert name]. I am doing research for the project PRESILIENT and I wondered if you would be interested in being involved. I am a researcher at the (institution). This project is a large network comprising 14 partners (of which 7 non-academic) and 15 associated partners located in Africa, Asia-Pacific and Latin America committed to delivering cross-regional training on informality in the Global South to: measure it, address it, find viable and sustainable alternatives. Can I tell you more about this study? [await confirmation].

This project is funded by the European Union. If you choose to be part of this project here is what will happen:

I will ask you questions about (...).

The answers you give me will form part of the project. Any personal information will be not be passed on to any third parties – only the team of the project will have access and they have all signed confidentiality agreements.

The research is confidential, which means that in any of the publications or reports your name will not be used. Later on we will make the anonymized dataset public but there will be nothing to identify you in these datasets.

We will be asking you about your political activities and opinions. We understand that this can be sensitive, and we will take care not to write up this research in any way which could be harmful to this community.

Taking part is completely voluntary and we can stop any time you like without giving a reason and without any negative consequences.

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With your permission, I would like to make an audio recording of our discussion to make sure I am getting an accurate record of your thoughts. Alternatively I can take notes in my notebook. Which would you prefer?

If you have any migrant links or civil society links I may want to re-contact you to ask some further questions. Would you be willing to be contacted again by us? This research will be published as academic publications and reports. You can find more and up to date information on the project on the website of the project and our research team. You can see the address of the website on the written information sheet I am leaving with you.

If you have any complaints or concerns, please feel to contact us [insert local contact number and email].

Do you have any questions?

Do you give your permission for to interview you/conduct the

survey? Do you give me your permission to record this interview?

Ok, thanks, in which case let's start. [If no recording] I am going to sign this form that says that you are ok with the interview.

Researcher record of oral consent

PRESILIENT: Post-pandemic resilient communities: is the informal economy a reservoir for the next generation of digitalized and green businesses in the Global South?

Interviewee name or Number [if anonymous participant]

Date:

Location:

Project and rights of participant explained (Yes/No)

[For qualitative interviewing or focus group only] Participant agree to recording of

interview (Yes/No)

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[For survey only] Participant agree to be re-contacted for follow up interview

(Yes/No)

Signature of researcher: _____

Signed in the presence of interviewee to confirm oral consent

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Annex III. Risk Mitigation

Risk mitigation recommendations for conducting research in non-European countries

Introduction

In this document PRESILIENT' ESRs and their advisors will find a general set of recommendations to address the eventual risks that for researchers and participants may arise during fieldwork. In this regard, research in general and fieldwork in particular should include an evaluation of the specific requirements in each country. This evaluation includes the following elements:

- A review of the political and security situation based on reports from international organisations.
- Continued consultations with colleagues/experts who have recently conducted research on related issues in these countries.
- Consultations with the travel advice of the Foreign Ministry of each Consortium member country.
- Affiliation of the researchers for qualitative fieldwork with relevant institutes in the respective countries where colleagues can facilitate local information and solutions if possible.
- Collaboration with local organisations.

The fieldwork should be carefully planned jointly between supervisors and ESRs.

First principle: Confidentiality

All personal data collected as part of the project will be kept confidential and fully anonymized before they are made available through dissemination of datasets and publications.

Method	Country	N per country	Output
Structured interviews			Anonymized dataset
Qualitative interviews			Anonymized summary of transcripts

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Participant observation	All fieldwork locations	General ad hoc follow up during fieldwork	Contextual descriptions. No sharing of the full fieldnotes.
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Second principle: Careful management of personal/sensitivity data

To avoid harming participants, the researchers will take great care to store any personal data relevant for contacting research participants. Potential participants will be contacted in person (survey), or via phone or email (qualitative research). Any possible identification of personal data or release of identity of participants shall be avoided by keeping in different files the addresses, phone numbers, email addresses and personal information that could allow any identification of the participants. The main dataset should contain contact details next to a pseudonym or a code in a separate file (no last names).

During and after fieldwork we will take care to store the data in a secure manner. All electronic information related to the survey and qualitative interviews (questionnaires, audio recordings) will be protected by password/pin-code to ensure that it is accessible only to the team members (and the subcontracted field research companies for the household surveys). Copies will be stored only on password/pin-code protected devices. Data will be transferred to the institutional servers and locked drawers/cabinets of the Consortium members through secure transfer via VPN or certificated mail.

During the analysis, transcriptions of qualitative interviews will be coded so that names of participants will be modified along a system of coding. In contrast, members of political elites by definition have a salient public profile, which means that much of the information regarding their background, networking and links are already out in the public domain, often as a requirement of them holding a public office. Still, in order to increase the participants' safety, the transcripts of both groups will not be shared with any third parties. Thus, the identities of the respondents belonging to local institutions or NGOs will not be disclosed, although the names of the organisations themselves might be identified indirectly.

All participants will be anonymous in the publication of research findings. Any presentation of intermediate findings will take care to withhold any information that may lead to the identification of research participants.

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Before beginning the field research, researchers will be adequately trained for fieldwork including possible types of compromising situations.

Third principle: Adequate positioning of ESRs during fieldwork

Another relevant aspect regards the positioning of the ESR while on fieldwork. Their positionality in terms of socio-economic background, gender and age can be important variables in entering the field and conducting the interviews, as well as during informal conversations and, more generally, when building ethnographic relations. Moreover, it is important to emphasise that each country of study has variations across regions.

The ESR will be aware of the impact of its presence in the field and will not actively seek information regarding issues potentially harmful to vulnerable groups, if the researcher happens to come across unexpected findings she may contact local NGOs or experts involved in these issues for an insider perspective and advice, but only in a manner that ensures the anonymity and respects the confidentiality of the participant.

The assessment of the need for intervention will include the need to be respectful of the local values and cultural norms as well as considerations of the legal rules and norms of the country of study. Attention will be paid to the effects that the disclosure of the finding may cause on the participant's and their family's well-being and exposure to hardship, as well as their general societal role. That is, an important part of the assessment will be to determine if the return of the incidental finding to the participant and related action would increase the risk for the participant rather than ameliorate it. Intervention will only be considered in extreme cases when there is a fear of the immediate harm to the 'material' or psychological well-being of the participant and where the researcher is legally bound to disclose this information. In case there is cause for serious concern that a reporting to the authorities could increase the exposure to hardship, alternative measures could be to advise the participant to contact a relevant NGO, social or legal services relevant to the particular issue at stake.

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Fourth principle: Adequate Incidental Findings management

In continuation, we elaborate the incidental findings policy by explaining how ESRs would deal with various types of incidental findings, although they are not exhaustive.

Human rights violations

The ESR should still immediately report the incidental finding to the supervisor in order to decide the best course of action. As there is not a very clear protocol for intervening in such cases, the best course of action would be to inform the participant of the existing national or/and local Human Rights Defenders Organizations. Such organisations can normally offer legal advice/support and, in some cases, they can also provide some form of protection.

Gender-based violence

Gender-based violence (GBV) is a significant problem worldwide. Nevertheless, coming across GBV during fieldwork is unlikely for several reasons. In case the participant reports an instance of GBV, this will result in the immediate interruption of the interview. The participant would probably be in great distress and may even require immediate assistance. The researcher will inform them with regards to the relevant local and/or national organisations, both governmental and non-governmental, that she can contact in seek for support/assistance.

Other incidental findings

Unexpected situations should be solved prudently and by contacting the supervisor and the local experts.

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